

WHY FOREIGN LANGUAGE IS IMPORTANT FOR ENGINEERS?

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the discussion of promising areas of teaching English for students of technical specialties. It deals with the modern problem of university methodology. The main incentive for the development of language education can be considered the practical needs of business. The requirements for foreign language proficiency for university graduates are constantly increasing, but the study of foreign languages often remains at the same level. When developing programs in foreign languages, it is advisable to take into account the specifics of training in technical universities, the ratio of different models of language learning in them: for general purposes, academic and professional communication.

Keywords: technical English, International language of professional communication, English for special purpose, teaching English in universities and colleges.

Teaching technical English is probably one of the most productive areas of English language teaching. Today, the demand for technical specialists who speak specialized English is growing all over the world. English is becoming the most influential language on the planet due to its prevalence. In the age of global globalization, the number of international industrial projects is steadily growing, leading to the growth of professional communication in English, which is increasingly strengthening its position every day. English has long been considered the most widely spoken language in the world. Of course, there are experts who do not recognize the objective fact of the dominance of the English language and give other data by speculating on the concepts of "wide spread versus the most widely spoken"; however, there is no doubt that this is the dominant language that is used in the international arena for professional communication with a certain degree of competence. English is referred to as "... the main language in the fields of international business communication, diplomacy, science and professional fields" [1].

For example, French engineers communicated with Egyptian colleagues in English during the recent construction of the metro in Cairo. Another clear illustration is the communication process at the international Swedish Volvo group, which has made English the official working language for its managers at

the plant in South Korea and even organized lessons for some of them during breaks. Many multinational corporations introduce English as a working language in their European offices. [1]

Without a doubt, the mandatory practice of language teaching in higher education is a significant achievement of Russian education, and we are not the only country that supports this position. Countries such as India, Denmark, Poland, and Romania also hold a similar point of view. The Technical University of Denmark, the Technical University of Lodz in Poland and the Technical University of Budapest in Hungary also offer technical English courses for their students.

It is well known that the programs of all Russian higher education institutions contain courses in English for Specific Purpose (ESP), which is defined as "... an area of English that focuses on teaching specialized sections of English in order to ensure the implementation of specialized scientific or work tasks" [2].

Recently, some specialists have been promoting the idea of the failure of the ESP and the absence of the need for such a course in general. It is proposed to replace ESP with EGP (English for General Purpose), which, in their opinion, will be quite sufficient for the formation of professional competencies among students of technical specialties. To begin with, let's try to figure out what the difference is, and then answer the question: to teach or not to teach specialized English.

The General English Course (EGP) is actually a primary and secondary school foreign language course. This is the basic stage of learning English. Students are introduced to the concepts of phonetics of the English language, are introduced to letter symbols, explain the features of grammatical and lexical constructions that form the discourse. EGP also focuses on teaching standard language skills for use in everyday life: various dialogues with classmates, teachers, friends, employees of shops, public institutions, etc. Students learn how to read and write correctly in a foreign language using previously read information from books, textbooks, newspapers, magazines, questionnaires and Internet pages. They also study the country-specific block as part of the process of cross-cultural communication.

ESP (English for Specific Purpose) or LSP (Language for Specific Purpose) – this concept is used to refer to a functional variety of language designed to ensure adequate and effective communication of specialists in a particular subject area. In other words, ESP or LSP means obtaining special linguistic knowledge for use in a professional environment or training in a specialty. ESP is aimed at a

narrower scope of application and prepares students directly for their future work, unlike EGP, which covers a broader scope of application, although the boundaries of competence are very often blurred. In general, the definition of ESP by contrasting it with a language for general purposes, which dominated in the 1960s, has given way to a new definition of ESP as a complete set of linguistic means used in oral and written texts.

Students of the University of Tamil Nadu (India) identified the following list of language competencies, which, in their opinion, is necessary for a further successful career in the field of IT technologies: speaking politely, using positive language, speaking convincingly, reporting, breaking the ice before talking to strangers, distinguishing between formal and informal speech, clarifying, persuading, active listening, writing reports, giving an oral presentation, speaking to a group (polite speech, use of positive language in speech, persuasive speech skills, report, establishing contact with strangers, the ability to distinguish between official and business languages, the skills of explanation, persuasion, active listening, writing reports, the ability to make an oral presentation, information message for a group of people) [3]. All these competencies can be equally attributed to both general and specialized English courses.

The development of a modern ESP program is a task that requires some effort and skills, which is not solved in one day. It requires a specialist philologist to have a certain training and knowledge of the basics of technology, the presence of elementary knowledge in mechanics, robotics, engineering, etc. Sometimes it is this feature of ESP that scares English teachers, because very often students are more competent in the technical part described using the language, which instills a certain uncertainty in the teacher and is a barrier that complicates the learning process.

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